

1 **Science eLetter (full version)**

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3 **adw2845: Host population structure reorganization supports coexistence of**
4 **multiple viruses**

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6 Ferdi L. Hellweger (1)*

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8 (1) Water Quality Engineering, Technical University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany

9 *Correspondence: ferdi.hellweger@tu-berlin.de

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12 **Main text**

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14 In their Research Article “Diverse phage communities are maintained stably on a clonal bacterial host”
15 (12 Dec 2024, p. 1294), Pyensen *et al* (1) present laboratory experiments that show multiple viruses
16 coexist on one host, and suggest these observations are transferable to natural conditions. To avoid
17 host evolution, they introduce fresh cells at every dilution. This is sensible, but also not realistic and
18 avoids feedback and resource limitation. Niche specialization can support coexistence, but in this case
19 the various host phenotypes/sizes are linked and may not function as different resources (2).
20 Specifically, a virus specialized on smaller/younger cells will reduce their concentration, which will
21 eventually also depress that of larger/older cells. If that is too low to support a virus specializing on
22 older cells it will go extinct, and *vice versa*. This classic resource limitation argument should apply
23 here, but is eliminated by the experimental design.

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25 I was curious about this and extended the model of *Levin et al* (3) to resolve host size classes, and then
26 simulated scenarios with a single host and multiple specialist viruses. The resulting model does indeed
27 predict coexistence throughout much of the parameter space (Fig. 1A&B). The number of viruses
28 coexisting depends on the assigned infection rates, but is limited by the number of size classes. The
29 underlying mechanism is reorganization of the host population structure: Consider a steady-state
30 situation with one virus specializing on older cells and a set of invasion experiments with a virus
31 specializing on smaller cells (Fig. 1C). With increasing infectivity of the later, it increases and smaller
32 cells decrease, which should also decrease larger cells. However, the decrease in smaller cells also
33 increases the substrate availability and growth rate, which effectively counteracts the decrease. I
34 conclude, consistent with Pyensen *et al* (1), that coexistence of multiple viruses on a single host is
35 possible under environmentally relevant conditions.

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 41 **Fig. 1. Size-structured model predicts the coexistence of multiple viruses on one host by**
 42 **population structure reorganization. (A)** Chemostat with oscillating coexistence. One host with 2
 43 size classes and 2 specialist viruses. **(B)** Number of coexisting viruses for models with $N = 2, 3$ and 10
 44 size classes. $N = 2^*$ simulation is with 3 specialist viruses. Diagnostic simulations with fixed size
 45 structure can only support up to 1 virus. **(C)** Coexistence is supported by reorganization of host
 46 population structure. Top: Concentrations of host size classes 1 and 2 (n_1, n_2), specialist viruses 1 and
 47 2 (p_1, p_2), resource (r) and size class 1 fraction (f_1) vs. virus 2 infection rate factor ($\delta_{2,2}$). Bottom:
 48 Causal chains for different regimes. (1) Increasing virus 2 infection rate is not enough to support virus
 49 2 and it does not establish. (2) Increasing virus 2 infection rate increases the virus 2 concentration (p_2)
 50 and decreases host size class 2 concentration (n_2). Normally this would lead to a proportional decrease
 51 in host size class 1 concentration (n_1). However, the decrease in host size class 2 concentration (n_2)
 52 increases resource concentration (r), which increases the growth rate and counteracts the decrease in
 53 host size class 1 concentration (n_1). (3) Increasing virus 2 infection rate increases the virus 2
 54 concentration (p_2), which decreases host size class 2 concentration (n_2), which decreases host size
 55 class 1 concentration (n_1) below that required to support virus 1 (p_1).
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58 Model details

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- 60 • The model of Levin, Stewart and Chao (3) (L77) was extended to resolve multiple size
 - 61 classes.
 - 62 • The model code is available from the author's GitHub page: <https://github.com/fhellweger>
 - 63 • State variables, equations and parameters are listed in Tables S1 – S4.
 - 64 • The implementation of the size-structured component was tested by comparing models with $N =$
 - 65 $1, 2$ and 10 size classes (Fig. S1)
 - 66 • The model was benchmarked against that of (3) by comparing to Fig. 4 of the reference, as
 - 67 shown in Fig. S2 here.
 - 68 • Note that the state variable for infected microbes (m) includes infection of each size class by
 - 69 all viruses. It is only used for substrate consumption (Eq. S1) and for that process the identity
 - 70 of the infecting virus is irrelevant.
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73 **Table S1. Model state variables**

Symbol	Units	Description
r	μg/ml	Resource
n_i	no./ml	Clean host, size class $i = 1 \dots N$
m_i	no./ml	Infected host, size class $i = 1 \dots N$
p_j	no./ml	Virus, type $j = 1 \dots M$

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Table S2. Model equations

Equation	No.
$\frac{dr}{dt} = \rho (C - r) - \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i (n_i + m_i)$	S1
$\frac{dn_i}{dt} = n_N \frac{\phi_N}{e_N} 2 - n_i \frac{\phi_i}{e_i} - \rho n_i - \sum_{j=1}^M \gamma_{j,i} n_i p_j$; for $i = 1$ $\frac{dn_i}{dt} = n_{i-1} \frac{\phi_{i-1}}{e_{i-1}} - n_i \frac{\phi_i}{e_i} - \rho n_i - \sum_{j=1}^M \gamma_{j,i} n_i p_j$; for $i > 1$	S2
$\frac{dm_i}{dt} = \sum_{j=1}^M \gamma_{j,i} n_i p_j - \rho m_i - e^{-\rho l} \sum_{j=1}^M \gamma_{j,i} n_{i,t-l} p_{j,t-l}$	S3
$\frac{dp_j}{dt} = b e^{-\rho l} \sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_{j,i} n_{i,t-l} p_{j,t-l} - \rho p_j - \sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_{j,i} n_i p_j$	S4
$\phi = \frac{P}{Q+r}$	S5
$f_i = \frac{2N}{(N+i-1)(N+i)}$ (a)	S6
$P_i = \frac{P}{N f_i}$ (a)	S7
$e_i = \frac{e}{N(2 - \sum_{k=1}^i f_k)}$ (a)	S8

77 (a) Calculations based balanced growth in steady-state chemostat or periodically-diluted batch culture, without virus.

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Table S3. Model input parameters

Symbol	Units	Value for Fig. ...					Notes
		L77(a) S2 S3	1A&B S1D S4 S5A&C	1C S1C	S1A&B	S5B	
ρ	1/h	0.45 (0.20-0.70)	0.30 (0.05-0.70)	0.48	-	-	
C	μg/ml	25 (10-40)	12 (5.0-40)	12	25	5.0-40	
e	μg/no.	1.35e-5	-	-	-	-	
γ	ml/no./h	6.24e-8	6.24e-8	6.24e-8	3.0e-9 (b)	6.24e-8	× δ (Table S4)
b	-	98	-	-	-	-	
l	h	0.5	-	-	-	-	
P	μg/no./h	9.96e-6	-	-	-	-	
Q	μg/ml	4.0	-	-	-	-	
dtD	h	-	-	-	24	24	
rD	-	-	-	-	50	2.3-2.5e7 (c)	

81 (a) Basecase (range). Parameters for original model based on Figs. 1 and 4 in Levin, Stewart and Chao (3).

82 (b) adjusted to get approx. same VBR in Fig. S1B and S1C.

83 (c) Corresponds to range of flow rates in Fig. S5A, $1 / (rD + 1) = \exp(-\rho dtD)$.

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Table S4. Infection rate factors (δ) (a)

	Value for Fig. ...				
	S3	1A&C	1B, S4, S5A&C	S5B	S1
Virus 1	1.0	1.58, 0	$\frac{N=1}{N=1}$ Exp. 1: 1.0 $\frac{N=2}{N=2}$ Exp. 1: 1.58, 0 Exp. 2: 1.43, 0 $\frac{N=3\&2^*}{N=3\&2^*}$ Exp. 1: 2.10, 0, 0 Exp. 2: 1.90, 0, 0 Exp. 3: 1.90, 0, 0 $\frac{N=10}{N=10}$	$\frac{N=1}{N=1}$ Exp. 1: 1.0 $\frac{N=2}{N=2}$ Exp. 1: 2.25, 0 Exp. 2: 0.75, 0 $\frac{N=3\&2^*}{N=3\&2^*}$ Exp. 1: 3.00, 0, 0 Exp. 2: 1.00, 0, 0 Exp. 3: 1.00, 0, 0 $\frac{N=10}{N=10}$	1G: 1.0 2G: 1.05, 1.05 2S: 1.58, 0

			Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 5\%$	Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 50\%$	
Virus 2	-	0, 2.85	$N=2$ Exp. 1: 0, 2.85 Exp. 2: 0, 3.15 $N=3&2^*$ Exp. 1: 0, 3.17, 0 Exp. 2: 0, 3.50, 0 Exp. 3: 0, 3.17, 0 $N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 5\%$	$N=2$ Exp. 1: 0, 1.50 Exp. 2: 0, 4.50 $N=3&2^*$ Exp. 1: 0, 1.67, 0 Exp. 2: 0, 5.00, 0 Exp. 3: 0, 1.67, 0 $N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 50\%$	2G: 0.95, 0.95 2S: 0, 3.2 (b)
Virus 3	-	-	$N=3&2^*$ Exp. 1: 0, 0, 4.75 Exp. 2: 0, 0, 4.75 Exp. 3: 0, 0, 5.25 $N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 5\%$	$N=3&2^*$ Exp. 1: 0, 0, 2.50 Exp. 2: 0, 0, 2.50 Exp. 3: 0, 0, 7.50 $N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 50\%$	-
Virus 4+	-	-	$N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 5\%$	$N=10$ Exp. 1: $\sim 1 / f_j \pm 50\%$	-

87 (a) **Definition and usage:** The infection rate (γ) is multiplied by this virus and size class specific factor (δ). For example: For
88 model in Fig. 1B, with $N = 2$ size classes and specialist virus infecting larger cells: $\gamma_{2,2} = \gamma \times \delta_{2,2} = 6.24e-8 \times 3.15 = 1.97e-7$.
89 **Parameterization:** Baseline value for specialist viruses set to result in equivalent infection rate as generalist virus, calculated
90 based on theoretical size fraction (Eq. S6). To avoid identical infection rates for multiple specialist viruses, which may result
91 in unstable coexistence, they were then varied. For example: For model in Fig. 1B with $N = 2$ size classes and specialist
92 viruses infecting small and larger cells: $\delta_{1,1} = 1 / f_1 \times 0.95 = 1 / 0.67 \times 0.95 = 1.43$, $\delta_{2,2} = 1 / f_2 \times 1.05 = 1 / 0.33 \times 1.05 = 3.15$.
93 Exp. 1, 2 and 3 refer to different experiments, with slightly different infection rate factors.
94 (b) Set to result in coexisting viruses, see Fig. 1C.

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Additional results

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101 Fig. S1. Examples of model simulations with a host with $N = 2$ size classes and 1 generalist virus (1G,
102 red), 2 generalist viruses (2G, green) and 2 specialist viruses (2S, blue). (A) Periodic dilution with
103 removal of old cells and addition of fresh growth medium and cells, i.e. as in P24. (B) Periodic
104 dilution with addition of fresh growth medium. (C) Chemostat, stable. (D) Chemostat, oscillating.
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Fig. S2. Testing of size structured model. Results of models with $N = 1, 2$ and 10 size classes. No viruses. Lines are exactly overlapping.

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Fig. S3. Benchmarking against L77 model and testing of size structured model. Results of models with $N = 1, 2$ and 10 size classes and 1 generalist virus. Existence defined as $n > 10$ no./ml, as L77. See Fig. 4 of L77. Lines are exactly overlapping.

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Fig. S4. Example of virus coexistence, within the host existence space (see Fig. S3). Host with $N = 2$ size classes, 2 specialist viruses, substrate inflow concentration (C) = 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Exp. 1 and 2 have slightly different infection rates (see Table S4).

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 125 Fig. S5. Summary of virus coexistence, within the host existence space (see Fig. S3). (A) Coexistence
 126 for non-exclusive infection (e.g. virus $j = 5$ infects mostly host size classe $i = 5$, but also $i = 4$ and $i =$
 127 6 , see Table S4). (B) Coexistence in periodically-diluted batch culture, i.e. as in Fig. S1B. (C)
 128 Coexistence when population structure is fixed (diagnostic simulation).

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131 References

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